

A Study of Thangka Painting in Contemporary Arunachal Pradesh

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Today, the Thangka Painting is widely known to the world. The thangka painting is painted on canvas (cloths) and walls (mural). It developed with the flourishing of the Tibetan Buddhist and gained recognition and appreciation for its intricate details, vibrant colours, beauty and artistic excellence. The world known as thangka painting is found in Tibet (China), Nepal, Bhutan and parts of India like Sikkim, Ladakh, Himachal Pradesh and Arunachal Pradesh.

Arunachal Pradesh is the largest state of North-East India, inhabited by many tribes of different religions/cultures. Tibetan Buddhism is one of the major religions of Arunachal Pradesh. The Tawang Monastery in the Tawang district is one of the largest monasteries in India. It is a living monument of Thangka or mural Paintings on its walls.

In this paper, the researcher introduces the thangka/mural painting of the Tibetan Buddhist culture. And attempt to outline the contemporary scene of the thangka painting and the state of practising artists of Arunachal Pradesh in the present scenario.

Keywords: Thangka painting, Tibetan Buddhism, Mural painting, Contemporary, Tradition, Tawang, Arunachal Pradesh.